

Yashil IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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No 4

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
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- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

74-91 xalqaro daraja
ISSN: 2992-8982

Yashil **IQTISODIYOT** va **TARAQQIYOT**

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Elektron nashr. 1056 sahifa.

E'lon qilishga 2024-yil 30-aprelda ruxsat etildi.

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Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

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CROSS-CULTURAL MANAGEMENT IS A SEPARATE FIELD OF SCIENCE AND DISCIPLINE

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Abstract: This article provides an overview of the history of cross-cultural management as a separate field of study. It highlights the importance of cross-cultural management in a globalizing world and takes the reader through the stages of research studies devoted to this field that have evolved into a separate discipline across the universities in developed economies.

Key words: culture, management, corporate culture, national culture, multicultural structures, human resources, cultural differences, mentality.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada madaniyatlararo menejment tarixi alohida tadqiqot sohasi sifatida ko'rib chiqilgan. U globallashayotgan dunyoda madaniyatlararo menejmentning muhimligini ta'kidlab, rivojlangan mamlakatlar universitetlarida alohida fanga aylangan ushbu sohaga bag'ishlangan tadqiqot bosqichlari bilan kitobxonni tanishtirib o'tadi.

Kalit so'zlar: madaniyat, menejment, korporativ madaniyat, milliy madaniyat, ko'p madaniyatli tuzilmalar, inson resurslari, madaniy farqlar, mentalitet.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлен обзор истории межкультурного менеджмента как отдельной области исследования. Она подчеркивает важность межкультурного менеджмента в глобализирующемся мире и знакомит читателя с этапами исследований, посвященных этой области, которые превратились в отдельную дисциплину в университетах развитых стран.

Ключевые слова: культура, менеджмент, корпоративная культура, национальная культура, мультикультурные структуры, человеческие ресурсы, культурные различия, менталитет.

In writing this article the range of publications of foreign and domestic scientists related to Cross-Cultural Management has been used. In particular textbooks and results of scientific papers have been thoroughly revised. For instance, the publications of Martin J. Gannon and Karen. L Newman's "Handbook of Cross-Cultural Management", Marie Joelle Browaeys, and Roger Price's "Understanding Cross-Cultural Management" (fourth edition), Veronica Velo's "Cross-Cultural Management", V.G. Bunina's "Cross-Cultural Management and Cross-Cultural Communication", Rafiul Abedin Chokder and Paulina Vanessa Díaz Tapia's "The role of corporate culture in managing cultural diversity, "Intercultural communication" in S. Bochner (ed.), Cultures in contact: Studies in cross-cultural interaction (pp. 61 79). Oxford: Pergamon have been widely utilized.

In modern society, the problem of cross-cultural management associated with the functioning of multinational, multicultural structures of modern international organizations has become increasingly relevant. The success of international business depends on understanding of the peculiarities of the national culture of other countries, the ability to adapt to the cultural differences of nations. It is the national culture that significantly affects the behavior of people and decision-making in the organization.

Moreover, it is worth noting that society is changing, digitalization of all life processes is taking place, and diversity of nations, languages, origins, gender, and appearances is becoming a norm of life. At this point, there is a clear consideration that the creators of global artificial intelligence cannot be allowed to be exclusive of one gender, ethnicity, age, or culture.

Thus, given the intersectionality of ethnocultural factors on digitalization, particularly the algorithmization of society, the question arises of how to manage these processes effectively and what technologies to use in doing so.

But, despite the growing interest and the number of studies, in domestic sociology, the problem of managing cross-cultural relations in an organization is still in the initial stage of development.

Each nationality has special behavioral and interpersonal individual behavioral traits, which also depend on the national culture. The behavioral patterns play a vital role in the functioning of any organization. In international companies where the composition of employees is largely diverse, the behavioral issues, cultural differences, and perceptions grow in importance and managers may face challenges in running a company. To understand, and most importantly, to effectively manage human resources in a transnational corporation, it is necessary to regulate their behavior following the individual cultural peculiarities of representatives of the national culture.

Why do we highlight cross-cultural management as a separate field of science? Theoretical rethinking of the laws of communication of business cultures has started since World War II, though in reality in practice, the issues of cross-cultural management, so as managing the processes of business communication are as old as the economy itself. Business communication at all times in all cultures always has been based on the national vision of the world, national cultures, and on national mentality. Why did 40 years ago in the 50-60th of the last century this problem concentrate in a separate discipline and grow into the main object of research? Most researchers believe that this is related to globalization which has been boosted by a sharp increase in international economic relations in the post-war recovery period.

The realization of Marshall's Plan, the penetration of the American economy into foreign markets, and the elevating of these plans to the US government policy have become the pushing factor in the emergence of Cross-Cultural management. Active economic US expansion quickly revealed the first challenges and failures associated with non-economic, national-cultural particularities of various countries. This necessitated American experts to effectively work out technologies and strategies to promote economic US interests in different nation-economic environments.

In the 60-70th a group of US scientists addressed new challenges that emerged at that time and commenced practical psychological and strategic recommendations, that would lead to the minimization of costs while building transnational corporations and promoting American interests. The first studies on cross-cultural interaction emerged after active US economic expansion. On the other side of the Atlantic integration processes that started in Europe aimed at creating a common economic area, also raised issues of effective cooperation of national economies.

Over 40 years cross-cultural has gone through the path reflecting the inner logic of the development of cross-cultural communication in the era of globalization.

The 1st cornerstone was related to the research that had been done on the issues of the penetration of large national companies into foreign markets globally. At this stage, by default, the concept of "Monoculture" was applied to penetrated markets as well as the concept of "national government". The studies made at that time have collected priceless materials characterizing the traits of national mentality, including business mentality.

Founders of cross-cultural management have conducted research and made analysis of many factors influencing the mentality of a nation. They concluded that such factors are historical, geographical, religious, and folklore. The socio-economic basis of each nation's value mattered under the propaganda of abstract "universal values" and averaged "human rights". The founders of CCM inferred: all nations are different, each has its system of values elaborated over many generations and cannot be modified without causing harm to the well-being of a nation. However, the research was limited to the statement of facts.

The second stage of the studies on CCM was related to the development of theories and typologies of corporate cultures about the issues of the international division of labor. It was noted that various national cultures gravitate towards different types of organization of economic progress, giving rise to different types of organizational behavior and forms of economic activity.

At this stage, studies on the types of corporate cultures appeared, based on the application of a national business mentality to the specific economic activity. A great achievement of CCM lies in the understanding that the corporate culture of the organization is based first of all on the national economic mentality. Secondly, corporate culture can be changed by considering its internal development paradigm.

The importance of the 80-90th research is that it reveals the interaction of corporate cultures and the application of the organization model to a particular national and

Currently, on the 3d stage, under the condition of growing migration processes and the critics of the "national government" idea, there is a necessity to comprehend a pattern of interaction of national business models not only in external economic activities but also intra-country activities, becoming more and more multiethnic and multicultural.

Cultural diversification of personnel across large and middle-sized companies raised the issue of including intercultural differences in traditional human resource management patterns, especially in the times of racial intolerance between citizens and migrants. In recent years, research on the management of "cultural diversity" has come to the forefront, aimed at developing mechanisms that would make it possible, while preserving

the national and cultural identity of certain groups of the population, to ensure sustainable and strict management control by developing some common, acceptable for representatives of different cultures “protocol” on cross-cultural management.

An additional impetus for these studies is given by the next round of geopolitical development – the processes of intercultural interaction in regional processes (in Europe, the Middle East, Latin America) show the similarity of the use of cross-cultural management mechanisms both in business and in geopolitics.

As a result of globalization, it is becoming more and more important for international managers to obtain specific cross-cultural knowledge and skills. Increasingly, effective adaptation in culturally diverse contexts is expected of individuals working in international settings, as this improves their performance. This involves - among other attributes and skills - successful interaction and coping with members of different cultural groups. Managers should therefore possess the special competencies and attributes that enable them to deal effectively with the rapid changes in the business environment and to communicate effectively on the international sphere; this is referred to as cross-cultural competence which has become a critical driver of international performance.

This is in line with the target of today’s universities in the present era of globalization. In recognition of global interdependence, there is now a high degree of interest and demand for global citizenship in education (GCE) (Simon, 2014). Universities are now pursuing producing “global citizens” to the workplace (Erez, Lisak, Harush, & Gilkson, 2013), graduates who can fit everywhere.

This is to be achieved by integrating an international and intercultural dimension of high quality and a competitive structure into the teaching, the research and the service functions of all institutions working in the field of higher education (Simon, 2014).

It is not surprising that universities are now calling for “becoming a global citizen” and marketing “schools that provide international career pathways”, emphasizing a globalized education equipping students with “employable skills in the international markets”.

Uzbekistan government also takes crucial steps in improving education and intellectual human resources. Over the past decade, many reforms have been implemented by Uzbek government. The reforms aim to utilize available material economic and intellectual resources efficiently. Their main goal is to prevent further decline of the standard of life of the citizens and to soften the negative impact of external factors influencing the entire world. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the official Decree № PF-4947 as of the 7th of February 2017 in “The Further Developments of the Republic of Uzbekistan” determined the Fourth Priority Direction in “The Actions Strategy”¹, which is enhancing the quality of School Education and in Specialized and Higher Education and taking measures to further prosper this sphere.

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¹ “O‘zbekiston Respublikasini yanada rivojlantirish bo‘yicha Harakatlar strategiyasi to‘g‘risida” O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2017-yil 7-fevraldagi PF-4947-son Farmoni.

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Jtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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2024. № 4

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Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

